

Spirit and Grace, Letters and Voice

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1. Ivan Illich, C. S. Lewis, J. K. Rowling, and Gratuitous Grace¹

Ivan Illich was born in 1926,² the same year as the priest, physicist, and philosopher Patrick Aidan Heelan, S. J. (1926-2015).³ I took a course in the philosophy of science with Heelan, who was also the first to introduce me to C. S. Lewis, and, almost in the same breath, to Ivan Illich's personality (Heelan and Illich were friends) and to Illich's work. It is perhaps no accident that Heelan (in what he intended as a spiritual context) would also tell me about Harry Potter by comparing me to Harry Potter. I had not yet read the novels, but given the comparison, I promptly read the first book, *Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone* as it is called in the American edition,⁴ and after that, of course, I never stopped reading them. Between the books and the films, I came to realize that if Heelan's comparison was ultimately not particularly accurate, the enduring beauty of Harry Potter, given the workings of the culture industry as Adorno details this, together with Illich's analysis of school as a schooling-in bourgeois society, is that *everyone* can be compared to (or take themselves to be) Harry Potter.

Now Ivan Illich was the Slavoj Žižek of the 60s and 70s, as a proponent of distinctly Catholic liberation theology, very radically, very broadly, conceived.⁵ And just as it is not a 'good thing', generally speaking, to be compared with Slavoj Žižek, it is similarly not a good thing to be part of liberation theology. An advocate of and for health *contra* what he named 'medicalization', a scholar of the word and the book against school, and a thinker about, and therefore a critic of, technology in our modern age, Illich would die, as he lived, among friends, in Bremen in 2002. In the intervals between writing lectures and books, Illich did the things that made him famous as one of our best candidates, apart from Dorothy Day, for sainthood (one does not always admire such exemplars: I met Dorothy Day when I was a kid, and found, as kids will, rather a lot to be desired in her style of austerity). Saints are meant to be ascetics and Illich surely shared that style, to such an extent that both his admirers and his detractors agree that his asceticism ultimately fell short, lamenting his appreciation for good food and wine, as if wine were not part of the heritage of the sacrament itself, and, indeed, of that other god, Dionysus.

2. 'Umsonstigkeit' – Gratuitous Grace

I read Ivan Illich's *Deschooling Society* (1971) together with his reflections on *Medical Nemesis* (1974) but also in connection with a work that appeared some two decades later: *In the Vineyard of the Text* (1993). By and large, Illich criticized institutions as such, not because he disagreed with them in the ideal — no more than did John Cardinal Newman or Illich's fellow Viennese compatriot, Ludwig Wittgenstein, or the British political theorist and philosopher of education, Michael Oakeshott — but precisely because he disagreed with them in practice.

Reflecting on institutions in one of his last texts, “The Cultivation of Conspiracy,”⁶ Illich reminded his listeners of the “kiss of peace”⁷ as legitimating intimacy and recognition, which Illich, using a tactic not unrelated to Heidegger’s more esoteric philosophical method, traced through a reflection on the meaning of words — tacking through atmosphere and its layers, the aura — to speak of smell *and* of suffering what one was forced to smell, the breath *and* breathing with, literally: con-spiracy, not as something to challenge, much less avoid, but and much rather to “cultivate” for the sake of an elusive “peace,”⁸ the peace a priest commemorates to, for, and with his conspirators, his concelebrants, his congregation. For Illich, who always remained a priest, his conspirators were his friends, and he meant this not in a loosening or casual sense but as a kind of informal but patent monasticism: “I have never doubted” he wrote — “and it’s even more true today — that a ‘monastic’ ambience is the prerequisite to the independence needed for a historically based indictment of society” (Illich, “Cultivation” 241). For Illich, “Community in our European tradition is ... the consequence of a conspiracy, a deliberate, mutual, somatic, and gratuitous gift to one another” (“Cultivation” 235). In this way, a few years before his death, at a moment of celebration, Illich offered this comparative reflection, recalling a certain corporeal shock to the sensibilities imposed first by the sense of smell and the body and what this means for spirit, as well as the very language of the “kiss of peace,” where we, just in order not to have to pay attention to the kiss, focus on peace, *pax*; Illich called this focus a distraction, and thus we shake hands during mass today, politely, resisting conspiracy as we do.

Illich writes:

The Latin *osculum* is neither very old nor frequent. It is one of three words that can be translated by the English “kiss.” In comparison with the affectionate *basium* and the lascivious *suavium*, *osculum* was a latecomer into classical Latin, and was used in only one circumstance as a ritual gesture: In the second century, it became the sign given by a departing soldier to a woman, thereby recognizing her expected child as his offspring. (“Cultivation” 239-240)

Illich’s point would be that congregants had to be close enough to inhale one another’s breath, and the community involved would have to presuppose the same:

Eucharist. *Conspiratio*, the mouth-to-mouth kiss, became the solemn liturgical gesture by which participants in the cult-action shared their breath or spirit with one another. (“Cultivation” 240)

At stake for Illich was the intractability of the same spirit that blows where it will, that is not up to us, that is precisely not as we will.

From this reflection on spirit, Illich drew a striking set of observations that we ignore in thinking about the philosophy of education and school at our peril: institutions and

centers, even those founded by persons with the charisma, the grace and gifts, of an Ivan Illich, could not, so he argued, be maintained, sustained, or preserved.

Illich argued that it was of the essence of spirit — and its clear paradox — that

atmosphere invites the institutionalization that will corrupt it. You never know what will nurture the spirit of *philia*, while you can be certain what will smother it. Spirit emerges by surprise, and it's a miracle when it abides; it is stifled by every attempt to secure it; it's debauched when you try to use it. ("Cultivation" 236)

Thus reflecting on the challenges of institutions as such, Illich's reflections on education, medicine, and technology explore the art of living in terms of mortality, but also as *open to* — and this is where it gets hard — as *generous* to others in their mortality, their vulnerability. Here we note that Illich's *Umsonstigkeit* is virtually untranslatable into English or, indeed, into German.

The standard English rendering in David Cayley's impressions of his conversations with Illich, *The Rivers North of the Future*, opted for simple "gratuity."⁹ I think it essential to hear the German: *Umsonstigkeit*, that is: something given for no good reason, no reason at all, *for nothing at all*, supererogatory beyond exchange and market price, apart from any expectation of any reciprocity, any *quid pro quo*, any aspiration to gain or advantage, *utterly* gratuitous. *Umsonstigkeit* is thus the unexpected, corresponding to no obligation, excess, beyond rule.

This kind of excess is akin to Nietzsche's affirmation or "yes saying," and, in this measure, Illich's *Umsonstigkeit* has a Goethean aspect, as we may recall that Pierre Hadot celebrated Goethe's view that "Only the present is our happiness" (Hadot, "Only" 217).¹⁰ Illich's celebration is golden, or in Goethe's words, „*Herrlich wie am ersten tag*“ („Faust," ed. Beutler 149). But the allusion to gold already warns us to take care: as Nietzsche emphasizes at the beginning of *The Gay Science*, the challenge for most of us is to see the good of goodness just where there is no advantage, no purpose, no point. Seeing what might, in such a fashion, be what is 'good', i.e., that it is good, isn't a matter of 'value' as Illich tries — not altogether successfully — to convey to Cayley, nor is it a matter of rule or calculation and also, ultimately, a matter of reasoning; it is hence inexplicable, irreducible to the good of the ideal of moral law, the categorical imperative.

3. On the Professor as 'Acteur' and the Culture Industry: Reflections on Alan Rickman

Popular books and movies are always manufactured in accordance with what Theodor Adorno named the 'culture industry'; witness the recent flair and fade of *Pokemon Go*, *Doctor Who* and *Doctor Strange*, *Wonder Woman* too, the *X-Men*, *Star Wars* and *Star Trek*, and not least the *Harry Potter* formula, and its franchise and offshoots and prequels too, its Disney World-style theme park surely included. In what follows, I read the performance practice of the late Alan Rickman (1946-2016) as Severus Snape as an

indispensable guide, if only because Rickman was an actor who played evil brilliantly, rife with ambiguity, edged with surprise, *contra* our more automatic prejudices.¹¹ As Rickman plays Snape's aspect, *ressentiment*-laden, this aspect includes unrequited and *therefore* pure and unsullied love: it is just this lack of consummation, this virginity, that matches Snape with Harry's mother, such that he can say "always," and it is why we believe him, just as we believe his unwanted attentions to Lilly not as so much mooning harassment but transfigured or redeemed in the undying dedication of romantic love¹² — and Rickman rather majored in this sort of romantic ideal. Indeed, if we were to count his roles, Rickman specialized in playing lovers, including a lover who is also a bad guy in *Love Actually*, or, more frequently, playing lovers of the risqué variety on stage in *Les Liaisons Dangereuses* or in Noel Coward's *Private Lives*, or, a bit more esoterically, if one will count the love of the world, speaking on behalf of God as Megatron in *Dogma*; or dramatizing a father's love, from incidental harassment become accidental perversion (*An Awfully Big Adventure*) to bereavement (*Snow Cake*), or as the 'wounded lover', in the already mentioned case of Snape or, else, classically romantically, in the case of Colonel Brandon in *Sense and Sensibility*; or, beyond death itself, as the lover who cares enough to return from the beyond for the sake of his bereaved partner in *Truly Madly Deeply*.

I am concerned to write about Rickman's 'acteurly' characterization of Severus Snape not as lover, that is as having been in love with Harry Potter's mother (think of the Oedipal fantasies that constellation can evoke, and has, in fact, evoked among a certain *Harry Potter* fan base) — a love utterly fantastic in every Lacanian sense, unconditionally loyal beyond the grave — but rather, and this is my focus in what follows, as a teacher at his most severe. True to the letter, Severus Snape's name, like everything in J. K. Rowling's books, tells us everything. And as the incarnation of the virtues of elocution, Rickman as actor justifies every syllable with every word he speaks, every pause, every eyebrow raised — only Leonard Nimoy's Mr. Spock was better when it came to the eyebrows.¹³

Note that I am mixing cultural references, combining high and low, as we do today without any particular trepidation. More critically it is worth asking what Illich, who has seen his time come and go, decades ago now, has to offer us today — especially with respect to philosophy of education, especially where Illich himself insisted on telling us to ban school, and who, as I have taken some care to illustrate, would further contend that the idea of the institution as such was bootless, as he argued spiritually, evocatively, at the end of his life. What can he say to us?

4. Latin and Letters

It is the letter, the alphabet, the text as such, that matters in Illich's beautifully titled, beautifully articulated *In the Vineyard of the Text*.¹⁴ And it is Latin that holds the key to the Harry Potter films and books, with their portentous names and elaborate incantations. Illich, talking about Hugh of St. Victor, is talking about Latin inasmuch as this 'dead' language dominates our relation to language, that is, to reading, as it does with grammar and syntax to this day.

Though he was a trained historian, Illich's point is not the tired notion of historical debt; much rather, he raises a hermeneutic question in a complex section entitled "The Latin Monopoly over Letters" (*Vineyard* 70-73), noting that history is nothing apart from the writing of empire: imperial expression, including imperial conflict and contest. To understand this, we need to reflect as Illich takes us back to the invention of phonetic writing, recalling that "[s]cholars increasingly recognize that truly phonetic writing was a one-time invention, made in Greece around 770 B.C." (*Vineyard* 102-103). Illich reflects on this point at some length, here and elsewhere, but his concern is not the Greek as such, important as this is for the distinction between oral and written cultures, specifically as a tool for the recording of sound. Instead, Illich here focuses on the political use of Latin, not *qua* record of a spoken *common language*, but as a legacy of rule and the prescribed use of letters. We still follow this rule, as Nietzsche once winced regarding this utter submission, as we continue to submit to the rule of grammar. As Nietzsche teases us on just this rule in *Twilight of the Idols*, "'Reason' in language: oh what a deceitful old woman! I fear we are not getting rid of God because we still believe in grammar" ("Reason" §5, 48). Illich's point is a more exoteric one: historically, to use the Roman alphabet was to commit oneself to writing in Latin; for a very long time, the Roman alphabet was not an alphabet that was used for writing other languages.¹⁵ And this dedicated commitment to Latin endured for centuries:

When we think of the alphabet, we see in it a tool for recording speech sounds. For one and a half thousand years this simply was not so. The letters, which without any change in form and number have proven their capacity to encode hundreds of different languages, were for this long time used for one exclusive purpose: writing Latin. But not Latin as it was spoken; rather, as it was alphabetized during the last centuries B. C. *During the 650 years when Rome governed the Mediterranean world, not one of the tongues of the conquered and governed peoples was ever recorded in Roman letters.* (*Vineyard* 70-71. Emphasis added)

As Illich continues his observation of Latin letters, he notes:

The monopoly of Latin over the Roman alphabet was so absolute that it has never been viewed as the result of a 'taboo', and has never been considered as a surprising historical anomaly. This neglect of an available technology seems as impressive as the neglect of the wheel in pre-Columbian cultures, where only gods and playthings were ever put on a carriage. (*Vineyard* 71)

Only a speaker like Illich himself, born in Vienna, displaced for historical reasons by war (and crimes against humanity) to Italy, and thus a native speaker of German who at a very young age learned Italian and French, and undertook to learn Croatian at the age of seven (in order, he tells us, to be able to speak with his Dalmatian grandfather), might have made such observations concerning the symbolic forms of the alphabet and of sound:

The monopoly of Latin over the Roman letters, and equally of Greek over the Greek alphabet, was anchored in deep assumptions about the relation of shape and sound. When Cyril and Methodius, around 850, created “galagolic” as the appropriate language into which they could translate the Greek Bible for the Bulgarians, they also devised a new alphabet. They never thought of enlarging the Greek alphabet with a few signs needed to record Slavonic sounds. (*Vineyard* 71)

Illich makes things more esoteric by alluding to his compatriot, the theoretical linguist Uwe Pörksen, when talking about the efflorescence of interest in Provençal and German song and the role of Latin itself as a hinge between them.¹⁶ We could draw a similar set of distinctions in English (think of Mark Twain’s use of dialect in *Huckleberry Finn*).¹⁷ The discussion is inevitably subtle, and to follow it one will need to read Illich’s footnote reference to Peabody, after which one can add Parry and Lord and not less, so I have been arguing for some time, Nietzsche’s reflections on the “spirit of music.”

5. Alchemical Coding: Severus Snape on Compounding Asphodel with Wormwood

I have argued for a number of reasons, including its reflection on Nietzsche’s *pathos of distance*, that Rickman’s interpretation on screen proved indispensable to the character of Snape.¹⁸ And if it is said that Rickman was privy to Rowling’s secret concerning Snape, his background, his double agency, etc. and so on, what does not depend on author privilege is the (still-to-be-asked) question of Rickman’s influence on Rowling: this is the question of whether or not Rickman’s portrayal of that same secret as he articulated it throughout would have any influence on the figuring of that denouement at the time still and yet to be articulated by the author herself, who watched the very same films we watched.

In the context of Illich’s characterization of our own scopic era as “the age of the show” (“Guarding”),¹⁹ I have elsewhere argued that the *Harry Potter* phenomenon is less about reading than about film and video. Indeed, let us call this the *Game of Thrones* effect: today’s novelist — consider the Canadian fantasy writer R. Scott Bakker — does not consider himself or herself a success unless HBO comes calling.

But film or not, the connection with the text remains. Everything depends on the linguistic terms: the Latin of the spells, the names of the characters Potter, Dumbledore, Snape, including the almost Lacanian codification of *Voldemort*: “He-who-must-not-be-named,” as in the sibilance of the snake itself, the name of the house Slytherin, all along with the tones of Alan Rickman.

Alan Rickman, who played villains manifestly for the fun of staging villainy, also liked to insist on little things, from the first film to the last: the same costume, buttons buttoned down all over, *points de capiton*, as Lacan would say. The reason I speak of Rickman as *acteur* is here to emphasize the deliberate performance of *improvisation*. To this extent, adding elements of interest, sameness, precision, repression, Rickman played his

professor just a little differently than J. K. Rowling had initially written him into being (hence my wondering above if Rickman's performative contribution made a difference in the end).²⁰

In the *Harry Potter* films, we meet an actor with all the gifts of the stage in a film of costumes and magic, including "foolish" wand waving, including — we have already mentioned the importance of the Latin spells — what Snape himself denounces, no better way to call attention to it, as so many "silly incantations."²¹

Costume and special effects are to be sure an everyday affair at Hogwarts — it is a magical school. But what is not par for the course is Snape's language, as this surprises the viewer at the same time that it impresses his students; thus he dismisses the likelihood of their interest, a strategy that works to compound interest, especially as Snape simultaneously alludes to the promise of astonishing powers. The class in question, like chemistry (or alchemy), concerns magic potions, as he makes clear:

"There will be no foolish wand waving or silly incantations in this class. As such, I don't expect many of you to appreciate the subtle science and exact art that is potion making. However, for those select few ... who possess ... the predisposition ... I can teach you how to bewitch the mind and ensnare the senses. I can tell you how to bottle fame, brew glory and even put a stopper in death...."

Nevertheless: the whole point of Hogwarts turns on the use of wands. And what else are witchcraft and wizardry to be about, if not about those same incantations, however denigrated?

The fragmentary collimation here exemplifies what Derrida calls aposiopesis. Given standard movie coding, i.e., given that Snape is wearing black, it is not hard for us, even if everyone else is wearing black as well, to suppose ourselves to know which side he is on. And he doesn't smile. And if that be insufficient, we can remember the sorting hat scenario at the outset of the film: Maggie Smith's Professor McGonigal's separating students into different houses, including Gryffindor, the good guys, and Slytherin, the bad.²² Rickman's Snape might surprise us, although we hardly pay this any mind, by failing in this first teacherly scene to focus on Malfoy or the other Slytherins, as might be expected of the director of their house. Nor does Snape, in setting a series of difficult questions on potions and being seemingly keen on answers, pay any attention to the eagerly clever Hermione Granger, although her hand shoots up immediately in response to his questions, volunteering to answer the questions Snape sets to Harry.²³

The questions Rickman's Snape puts to Harry are, it should be remembered, not wholly all about putting him on the spot, although that is our first impression. Rather, what is at stake is preparation, in two senses. To this end, Snape poses a question about the subject matter of the class, which is precisely magic potions: "Tell me," he asks from a distance that highlights the impact of his question, "what would I get if I added powdered root of asphodel to an infusion of wormwood?" Here, in this context, 'asphodel' is a highly

poetic allusion, dating back to the very beginnings of poetry with Homer's reference in the *Odyssey* to the fields of asphodel where the souls of the dead dwell in the underworld, with echoes of Elysium. Asphodel appears in this context in works by Milton, Tennyson, Longfellow, and even Oscar Wilde.²⁴ More typically, it is pointed out that Snape's question seems to recall a love poem written by William Carlos Williams, "Asphodel, That Greeny Flower."²⁵ At the very least, the simple range of poetic recollection suggests that this was for Rowling an anagram of 'signatures', and thus the reference to alchemy befits a course on magic potions and a professor who, as we are told, Rowling modeled on a severe (obviously) professor of chemistry.

But in the film version, things move quickly, and Harry, dismally unequal to every question Snape poses to him, inspires only his teacher's sarcasm: "Pity. Clearly fame isn't everything, is it, Mr. Potter?" which strikes us today as not a supportive thing to say, seemingly confirming all our suspicions about Snape's sadism; and yet even there teacherly bullying doesn't seem to be the whole of it, as Snape whirls to turn his annoyance against the entire class: "Well, why aren't you all copying this down?"

I am spending this amount of time on a film series made for children, a film exporting a very English idea of school to other countries, including the US, France and Germany, to underline the force of language, which works because one can hear this in the *Latin* of the spells, as Rowling drew the magic of her book as a book about nothing so much as school, from nothing other than, or less academically linguistically significant than, Latin as such, *and* as a signifier.

Note the power of a word to conjure up the sense of important knowledge. This is the adept's beginning — alchemy once again — in Goethe's *Faust*, corresponding to both our aspiration to powers beyond our capacities and the limitations of our knowledge of those same limits. We recall Faust's first incantation and its intimation: "Thou, Spirit of the Earth, art nearer / ... / I glow, as drunk with new made wine" (Goethe, *Faust* 20).²⁶ The very same Spirit invoked, implored — Faust cries "I feel thee draw my heart, absorb, exhaust me: / Thou must! thou must! And though my life it cost me!" (21)²⁷ — does indeed respond, pointlessly as it turns out, simply to the extent that precisely as mortal beings we cannot hope to comprehend the metaphysical as such (this is one of the reasons theology needs philosophy, for the same reasons of analogy and proportionate knowledge), as the spirit rebukes Faust:

To view me is thine aspiration,
My voice to hear, my countenance to see;
Thy powerful yearning moveth me,
Here am I! — what mean perturbation
Thee, superhuman, shakes? Thy soul's high calling, where?
Where is the breast, which from itself a world did bear,
And shaped and cherished — which with joy expanded,
To be our peer, with us, the Spirits, banded?
Where art thou Faust, whose voice has pierced to me,
Who towards me pressed with all thine energy?

He art thou, who, my presence breathing, seeing,
Trembles through all the depths of being,
A wrinkling worm, a terror-stricken form? (21-22)²⁸

Here, as in the case of the beginning invocation of the spirit of the earth, inspired, as the literary scholar Burdach tells us that Goethe was inspired by Herder's poem „Das Kind der Sorge“ [“The Child of Care”],²⁹ while Herder himself was inspired by Hyginus — this also matters for Heidegger's reflections, ethical, I argue,³⁰ on care in his *Being and Time* — what matters for the conjurer (or sorcerer in the case of Harry Potter) is the sense of the right word perfectly chosen, precisely articulated, in the right way, for the right reason, and above all perhaps at the right time.

As in the case of a religious rite, here we may think of the Greeks of antiquity as Nietzsche reminds us in his own reflections on poetic rhythm, or we may think of Tibetan monks today, or the formula for a prayer, or, perhaps especially in the case of casting a magic spell, the formula word *Abracadabra*: it is the right gesture, the right placement and poise, as well as the correct enunciation that makes all the difference.

As a phenomenological philologist, Nietzsche argued that the role of rhythm concerned not its capacity to entrain our own souls but its objective force beyond ourselves, to move the cosmos itself. When we get to science we may think we can dispense with rhythm, rhyme, and every element of style or rhetoric. Thus Harry Potter is valuable, as Goethe's *Faust* is valuable, if only we can be led to pay attention to the importance of style and the signifiers of distinction, the way and the how of our speech, the role of subtleties.

6. Rhythm and Prayer: Towards a Phenomenological Philology

The focus has been on Ivan Illich, J. K. Rowling as author of children's literature, and to play and thus to unlock this coding on screen, Alan Rickman as actor. I have also referred to Homer and Milton, and to William Carlos Williams' “Asphodel, That Greeny Flower,” in addition to Goethe and Herder and Nietzsche. As a classical philologist, Nietzsche was an expert in Diogenes Laertius, and his particular research interest was Greek lyric, specifically quantizing, quantitational [*quantitierenden*] metric. Here we may recall that reflections on the lyric poet, including the lyric subject, were at the heart of Nietzsche's book on tragedy — not reflections on the person himself, but on the poem as such. I have argued this point in several different variations, but it is an elusive one.³¹

We separate, as Nietzsche tells us that we ought not separate, music and word. To this extent, when scholars tell us what ancient music ‘sounded’ like, as mainstream scholars are wont to do, their claims and discoveries are founded upon what is taken to be expressly, exclusively, musical notation supervenient upon the words themselves, and this assumption is operative even where we have no such notation from historical eras relevant to ancient Greek musical drama.³² The assumption is that ancient Greek music had its own script and that we simply need to find it, or otherwise reconstruct what we today would call the score.³³

As Nietzsche puts it in his lecture on Greek music drama, “One knows that tragedy was originally nothing other than a choral song.”³⁴ At issue is only the literality of this claim: “True Greek music is purely vocal: the natural link between the language of words is that of sound which had not yet been sundered.” (Nietzsche, “On Music and Word” 107). The problem is the origin of language,³⁵ expressed as the origin of music and lyric poetry, *qua* oral poetry, and thereby the original function of writing as a means for recording musical pitch.³⁶

In his Basel lecture courses on *Greek Lyric*, Nietzsche lists several steps beginning with

1. the introduction of orchestric-chorestic music from popular life into the contest ...
2. Adding to this pure instrumental music...
3. the system of tonal kinds develops out of Phrygian music....
4. Herewith begins the notation of music, the note system of the alphabet.... („Griechische Lyriker,“ *Werke* 403)³⁷

Emphasizing the musicality of the Greek word (*contra* the modern or emphatic stress-accent),³⁸ Nietzsche argued that for the ancients the “rhythmical [stress] ictus is unattested, shows no effect, was, rather, completely excluded” („Zur Theorie“ 277).³⁹ *Per contra*, Nietzsche differentiates a „ton-Iktus,“ reflecting that this cannot but be elusive for us, given our own modern linguistic sensibilities.⁴⁰

Phenomenological philology here illuminates Nietzsche’s point; it is the method that proves his case: “Why,” as he asks with reference to his own new innovation, “don’t we set the music *near* the word rather than *in* the word?” („Griechische Lyriker,“ *Frühe* 372. Emphasis added.),⁴¹ invoking the cult relevance of lyric poetry (hence the reflection above on *Vergegenwärtigung*), claiming that “the lyric is the oldest form of poesis” („Griechische Lyriker,“ *Werke* 379).⁴²

Thus when Nietzsche, as noted, cites a “4fold” („Griechische Lyriker,“ *Werke* 379)⁴³ rhythmic *efficacy* in this text as inherent to the use of the rhythmic word, this means that the Greek deployed rhythm as means for influencing, or even “compelling,” their deities — and this fact survives in magical formulae, once again: in the *abracadabra*, and, in the Harry Potter novels, the linguistic and filmic use of (often enough literarily licensed) Latin.

But as in the case of the beginning invocation of ‘the spirit of the earth’ at the start of Goethe’s *Faust*, what is at issue for the magician is the sense of the *mot juste* of which I have been speaking with respect to Nietzsche, as indeed to Illich.

When Illich refers to Peabody’s *The Winged Word*, he is referring to just this compelling context: the context of prayer and celebration as well as of recollection.⁴⁴ The point is not coincidental for Illich, who emphasizes here that

We sometimes forget that words are creatures of the alphabet. The Greek language originally had no word for ‘a word’ singly identified [*Illich*’s

*reference is Erik Havelock — BB]. Greek had only various terms referring to sounds and other signals or expressions: utterances could be articulated by the lips, the tongue, or the mouth, but also by the heart when it spoke to the friend by the *thymos* (which we might call “gall”) which rose in Achilles and drove him into battle, or by the onrush of a wave of blood. (*Vineyard* 39)*

Indeed, this is the rhythmic point that Nietzsche sought to bring out in his effort to articulate what he would come to call the “spirit of music,” and that is all about sound. As Illich helps to explain — reading Anne Carson’s *Eros, the Bittersweet* can also help us here, along with Illich’s earlier remark regarding the Greek as a one-off invention for the preservation of sound — in general

the alphabet is an elegant technology for the visualization of sounds. Its two dozen shapes trigger the memory of utterances that have been articulated by the mouth, the tongue, or the lips, and filter out what is said by gesture, mime, or the guts. Unlike other writing systems, it records sounds, not ideas. And in this it is foolproof: readers can be trained to voice things which they have never heard before. (*Vineyard* 39)

The elusive discussion in Illich of Marcel Jousse,⁴⁵ and the emphasis on gesture and rhythm in memory, in communication, and in prayer, is all part of this.

In what follows, Illich quotes Aristotle on form and orientation with respect to what for the Greeks became “the metaphysical constitution of the universe”:

Leucippus and his associate Democritus say that the full and the empty are the elements, calling the one being and the other non-being: the full and solid being being, the empty non-being. One substance (for them) generates all things ... and does so by three modifications, which are these: shape order and position. They say that the real is differentiated only by “rhythm” and “inter-contact” and “turning”. Of these rhythm is shape, inter-contact is order and turning is position. A differs in shape from N. AN differs from NA in order. H differs from Ξ in position. (Aristotle, *Metaphysics*, 34, 985b, cited in Illich, *Vineyard* 40)

At stake is not simply a mnemonic technique; what is involved is the essence of prayer, the reaching of the gods, as per Nietzsche; the word “with wings,” as Peabody’s title has it. Thus Illich writes:

When the child is rocked during a cradle song, when the reapers bow to the rhythm of a harvest song, when the rabbi shakes his head while he prays or searches for the right answer, or when the proverb comes to mind only upon tapping for a while — according to Jousse, these are just a few examples of a widespread linkage of utterance and gesture. (*Vineyard* 61)⁴⁶

Illich refers to Jousse with a gloss that has yet to be unpacked, explaining as it does a veritably *performative* physiology of prayer — the rabbi’s rhythmic bowing, shaking “his head while he prays,” is *davening* — noting that “Jousse was a French Jesuit stationed in Beirut, who spent his entire life in the study of the embodiment of Semitic sayings” (*Vineyard* 61, note 40).⁴⁷ And the point for Illich has everything to do with the monastic tradition, and this has everything to do with school.

Illich writes of the perfect coordination of meaning and sense, of relief, words, and rites as these can be felt by the child in an order in Hugh of St. Victor’s day, in our day, and for Harry Potter too:

Within a few weeks the child would associate the rustling of cloak at the end of each prayer with the rising of the monks and the *gloria Patri*. The rhythmic repetition of the gesture of rising and bowing and its coincidence with a small canon of short formulas was easily associated with pious feelings and habits even before the novice was able to spell out the literal meaning of the Latin words. *Deo gratias* — thanks be to God — is felt as a response of relief at the end of a long Bible reading which takes place in the middle of the night. So also in the refectory at noontime, it is the anxiously awaited sign that mealtime prayers are over and dinner may begin. (*Vineyard* 68)

For Illich, even before learning begins, there is an incorporation, an embodiment, essential for any approach to Hugh of St. Victor’s *Guide to the Arts*:

The ceremonial celebration of the book, Latin, chant, and recitation thus form an acoustic phenomenon embedded in a complex architecture of rhythm, spaces, and gestures. All this could not but stick to the bones of the pupils when, after a short sleep before dawn and two more morning assemblies for Mass and the “little” hours, they finally sit cross-legged in front of a drill master for their dictatus, to give shape with their hands — inscribing the words on their wax tablets — to the Latin in whose melodic use they were already steeped. (*Vineyard* 70)

7. Harry Potter and the Secret Life of Professors

As always, Illich is telling tales out of school, tales out of the life of scholasticism, as this has all but perished in our day. And yet it lives on, as in the example of Rowling’s *Harry Potter* — in Snape’s clerical garb, expressed perhaps in all of Rickman’s concern to get the sleeves long enough, and Harry’s too (along with the concern of Ron and every other student at Hogwarts), as all of this serves to indicate a point that anyone can make if called upon to give a commencement speech. To this day: all of us dress like monks when it comes to graduation ceremonies at school.

Here, to illustrate Nietzsche's rhythm, recall the dueling scene in *Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secrets*, featuring two British actors: the late Alan Rickman in his portrayal of Professor Snape in a scene counterpoised against Kenneth Branagh's Professor Gilderoy Lockhart. The scene is articulated by way of a very choreographed, very rhythmic fencing standoff on a table that serves as the fencing piste, wands as weapons in place of foil, sabre, and épée. What is at stake is poise, balance, and articulation. Those who try and fail in the spell do so because they do not speak the words, but, as Shakespeare tells us, "mouth them." The same holds for the wonderfully pompous, and once again note the name and its rhythms, Gilderoy Lockhart, such that after the appropriate bowing, and dueling back to back pacing off, the duel is settled not with wand flourishes but with a single word: Rickman's *Expelliarmus!* The dramatic efficacy of Snape's gesture and word renders Lockhart, flat on his back, out cold at the end of the table.

Secondly, and this is again the reference to Jousse as Illich emphasizes it, Nietzsche argues that the function of rhythm is to appease or to "purify" the feelings of the gods themselves (just as, as Nietzsche notes, music calls forth powerful human feelings), and Nietzsche argues that rhythm works, thirdly, as mnemonic aid for the deity (who would appear to have trouble remembering what is petitioned), in analogy with rhythm's functioning for human beings, where we have already emphasized, via Peabody's *Winged Word*, the fourth role of rhythm for Nietzsche: as a means to reach the distant heavens. In the same way, Nietzsche reprises these aspects of both rhythm and prayer in *The Gay Science*. To this same extent, it may be argued, all religious ritual, all magic, all prayer, is inevitably "sympathetic" magic. And here too Nietzsche's analysis of the death of tragedy would correspond to the ascendance of insurgent rationalism, because, as the sensibility for a more "natural causality awakens in place of a more magical causality, in the same measure, rhythm makes its retreat" („Griechische Lyriker," *Werke* 380).⁴⁸

By the time we have attained the advances of our modern era we believe in pure reason, and that also means that we are ill prepared to pay attention to the importance of language, the way and the how of our speech, the role of subtleties. Not because these things have ceased to be efficacious. Sociolinguists with an expertise in physiology have not analyzed the specific voice of an actor like Alan Rickman for nothing. It is claimed that it is due to a speech defect, that is to say, on Rickman's own account of it that his voice had the qualities it had not because he was born gifted but because he learned to work with and around his certain limitations. Lots of people today mumble or fail to enunciate for reasons that also have to do with the structure of their mouths, teeth, jaws, and in *The Hallelujah Effect* I point to qualities of sound that depend on the room as a sounding board, and to Adorno's argument that much of what we call the culture industry results from the translation of that resonance to radio sound (and the locative reduction to the loud speaker that subsequently entrains the mind), and what Adorno named "physiognomy."⁴⁹ By this phenomenological and carnal or embodied object-phrasing Adorno intended to refer to the literal acoustic, sonic translation in space, but also in time and above all in acoustic transformation, transposing an orchestra, a chamber quartet, a rock band from its original place-space, time-space into a little box (and it makes no difference here if we are referring to binaural earphones, per a single speaker, or a set of

boxes, high- or low-end, in our living rooms: we have yet to catch up to what Adorno meant when talking about the space-time continuum of music and sound).

8. Our Lives Are Measured Out by Teachers

Our teachers are sometimes thanked. More commonly they are forgotten, rather like the Suabian joke about a man, teetering home late at night, as drunk as can be imagined, coming to a narrow bridge to cross a stream, who in good piety stops to say a prayer to get safely across the bridge, only, attaining the half way point, to cry out jubilantly, declaring he could have managed very well on his own, which promptly lands him in the ditch. We tend to think we could have done everything without the particular teachers we happen to have had, even when we think to thank them, for appearances or politeness's sake. We are as wrong as the Suabian tipped by his pride into the nighttime water, muttering to himself, *Surely the Good Lord understands a joke?* Our inattention to our teachers is like that. Yet there they are, even if we only catch sight of their value in retrospect, like William Carlos Williams' singing of love (and disloyalty to his wife — that was the point of his poem "Asphodel, That Greeny Flower," sung from the bottom of hell).

To my mind, Alan Rickman meant something like this replying to an interviewer's question by saying, emphasizing that this can only be seen in retrospect, "Our lives are measured out by teachers." Beyond flesh and blood encounters, some of our teachers are also those we meet in the books we read: fictions like Severus Snape; but also those for whom Machiavelli would take care to dress up when he read, encounters with teachers never known in our lifetimes, teachers still living in the books we read.

Notes

¹ This essay grew out of a lecture originally presented in German in honor of Ivan Illich at a conference in Bremen. In its current version it was originally invited for presentation as a plenary lecture for the Society for the Philosophical Study of Education, Columbia College, Chicago, Illinois, 4 November 2016. The author is grateful to the editors of the journal and especially for the words of two anonymous reviewers.

² There is no definitive biography of Ivan Illich and, to date, most accounts of his thinking, including those that undertake to offer an account of his life as well as of his influence, differ in precision (not to mention their conflicting details) according to the orientation and concerns of the author in question. For the sake of hermeneutic reflection, it is best to read *between* accounts, and a good place to begin is with the different voices of the friends included in Hoinacki and Mitcham.

³ Patrick Heelan wrote on Werner Heisenberg's philosophy of quantum mechanics, and for a very readable discussion of the debates surrounding quantum mechanics, including those involving Niels Bohr and Albert Einstein, see his posthumously published *The Observable: Heisenberg's Philosophy of Quantum Mechanics*. And see, too, on the space of vision, including the art of Cezanne and van Gogh, Heelan's *Space-Perception and the Philosophy of Science*.

⁴ Cf. J. K. Rowling, *Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone* (London: Bloomsbury, 2000 [1997]) and *Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone* (New York: Scholastic, 1998).

⁵ See, for example, Schrag. See too, for a reading that is not always commensurate with Illich's life, Hartch. See, for a discussion, Babich, "Tools for Subversion: Illich and Žižek on Changing the World," in Mazzini and Glyn-Williams.

⁶ Illich, "The Cultivation of Conspiracy," speech presented at the Villa Ichon, Bremen, March 14, 1998, on the occasion of the receipt of the Culture and Peace Prize of Bremen. The lecture appears in English in Hoinacki and Mitcham 233-242.

⁷ On peace, here, Illich writes: "The European idea of peace that is synonymous with the somatic incorporation of equals into a community has no analogue elsewhere. Community in our European tradition is not the outcome of an act of authoritative foundation, nor a gift from nature or its gods, nor the result of management, planning, and design, but the consequence of a conspiracy, a deliberate, mutual, somatic, and gratuitous gift to one another. The prototype of that conspiracy lies in the celebration of the early Christian liturgy in which, no matter their origin, men and women, Greeks and Jews, slaves and citizens, engender a physical reality that transcends them. The shared breath, the *con-spiratio*, is peace, understood as the community that arises from it." Illich, "Cultivation" 241.

⁸ Indeed, and this is connected to his notion of *Umsonstigkeit* or freely given, unearned, gracious, ‘gratuitous’ grace.

⁹ Note here that ‘gratuity’ is a poor choice in English as it means tip or emolument, and ‘gratuitousness’ is not much better. See Cayley’s book conveying what Cayley took from his conversations with Illich.

¹⁰ Hadot elsewhere translates this line, „Die Gegenwart allein ist unser Glück,“ as “The present alone is our joy,” and describes it as “the climax of part two of Goethe’s *Faust*.” Hadot, “Forms of Life and Forms of Discourse,” in his *Philosophy as a Way of Life* (69).

¹¹ There is almost a parallel to Snape, I submit, in any case, though not since Goethe’s *Faust*, in the person of Mephisto (and there in performance, on stage as on screen, it is the actor who makes all the difference: think of Gustaf Gundgrens), and it will also help to recall that evil nearly always has a good conscience; thus Rickman in the UK television series *The Barchester Chronicles*, or as the mastermind Hans Gruber in the Hollywood film *Die Hard*, or as the Sheriff of Nottingham by contrast with the traditionally Jesus-like Robin Hood (not that this would have been Kevin Costner’s Robin Hood).

¹² Arguably this is the key to his villain’s heart in Snape, expressed by a white doe, his ‘Patronus’, in Rowling’s subversive invention.

¹³ To be sure, Rickman himself gives the raised-eyebrow award to his fellow Hogwarts actor, Maggie Smith.

¹⁴ With its own bookish reference, it is a commentary, or scholarly guide, to a scholarly guide. Illich’s *In the Vineyard of the Text* illuminates or offers the reader an opportunity to experience what the author writes about. There are details to discover, or perhaps even, to use Illich’s language, to ‘taste’, on every page; between every sentence, every word; ensconced in the footnotes, beyond what we ordinarily suppose about the things we read as about the art of reading as such. See too Illich and Sanders, and for a focus on Greek as well as Latin letters, see Carson.

¹⁵ As a tool for communication and control from its imperial outset, Latin letters were used to write Latin by those who knew and read Latin. When this began to change — that is, when Latin letters came to be used for the vulgate — the change corresponded to nothing less than an imperial appropriation. But to this day we speak of the Roman alphabet. Heidegger, and it is increasingly uncool to talk about Heidegger, makes this point as bluntly, and Illich is anything but ungenerous as he observes that scholars are increasingly coming to recognize the complexities of what follows from this dominion. Here, Illich’s example is a subtle one that can continue to elude us: thus we think and sometimes we even teach that the church somehow restricted the use of letters to Latin, ignoring a reflection on the relation between letters and language(s).

¹⁶ As Illich explains: “The alphabetic recording of Germanic or Provençal dialects did not immediately lead to the recognition that the alphabetization of speech had brought about the creation of other languages comparable to Latin. One of the best proofs for this comes from Uwe Pörksen. For the first two generations in which there was a heavy demand for Provençal texts in Germany, and vice versa, not one of the great songs was translated directly from one vernacular language into the other. In every instance, a Latin version of the song was made first, and only then a translation from the Latin language into recorded vernacular speech” (*Vineyard* 72-73). For a discussion of the oral tradition of the Provençal in its significance for Nietzsche as author of *The Gay Science*, subtitled in Provençal as “*la gaya scienza*,” see Babich, “Gay Science.”

¹⁷ I am grateful to Tracy B. Strong, who pointed out to me that Twain claimed, in order to testify to a non-British but American English, to use at least 7 dialects, and that others, according to Strong, count as many as 11.

¹⁸ See Babich, “Getting to Hogwarts,” and Babich, “Pedagogy and Other Defenses.”

¹⁹ See also Illich, *La perte des sens*, for his epochal history of vision, whereby the first optical regime of vision would later be characterized as the ‘agent intellect’ expressed in antiquity’s theoretical account of mind and optics: « Dans le régime antique, le regard rayonne depuis la pupille pour embrasser un objet, se fondre avec lui, au point que l’œil est teinté aux couleurs de l’objet. La fin de ce régime d’un regard qui embrasse tout commence dans l’Égypte des Fatimides, autour de l’an mil » (203). Illich goes on to articulate the second optical regime as that of the church, the monastery, and the university. This is the « régime scolastique [ou] le regard demeure actif », « mais la vision n’intervient plus où se trouve l’objet: l’œil a désormais le pouvoir d’extraire des universaux des formes que les choses émettent par leur rayonnement... Un troisième régime naît de l’union du regard et de l’objet à l’aube de la Renaissance; de plus en plus l’œil est perçu comme un instrument sur le modèle d’une caméra, d’un appareil photographique, dont diverses techniques permettent d’étendre la portée ... un quatrième âge est celui du show, un âge au cours duquel l’œil devient dépendant de l’interface (nos écrans) plutôt que de l’imagination » (197).

²⁰ Thus, likewise *qua* performance practice, the impact of Rickman’s Snape as master of potions in *Harry Potter and the Sorcerer’s Stone* (2001) could scarcely have been more dramatic. Entering from the rear of the class, door slamming, striding to the front with black cape flaring, Snape declaims from the moment he enters the class, silencing pre-class murmurs. It is Snape’s manner, particularly his way of speaking, that impresses children and adult filmgoers alike, including those too young to care about *Die Hard* (1988), where Rickman played a “real villain” (as opposed to Snape) by contrast with the American-style, torn t-shirt, utterly unbuttoned hero Bruce Willis; or else, to have been seen in the genre of ideal or noble love, again recall the importance of distance, *qua* initially unacknowledged, as the essence of romantic love for Rickman’s Colonel Brandon, who married Kate Winslett and starred with Emma Thompson in her

screenplay version, once again as film rather than book, of Jane Austen's *Sense and Sensibility* (1995).

²¹ Viewers familiar with Rickman recognize him despite his disguise (he wore a wig as the Sheriff of Nottingham in *Robin Hood: Prince of Thieves*). Yet several commentators point out that even at the start of the ten-year film franchise, the actor was too old, by decades, to play a Snape who should have been in his thirties, old enough to have been Harry's biological father but described in unappealing terms as extremely thin, greasy of complexion, complete with a barely kempt mane of black hair, head to toe in black, wearing a high topped vest, and with all those buttons that Rickman himself insisted upon.

²² Although a school of witchcraft and wizardry seems firmly located beyond good and evil, the dyadic division reflects our expectations of the good and the bad; and in the first class, the camera cuts to a knowing smile from the little Draco Malfoy, a lad to be groomed for negative things. Malfoy, as if his name didn't tell us this already, is evil, and Draco is blond, like his father. The dyadic coding in Harry Potter gives us Harry himself, dark haired, like Hermione. Ron, the redhaired kid, is a ringer, simply underwriting the convention locating Malfoy on the side of evil, sure to be among the 'select few' ones, possessing the needed 'predisposition'. The entire film-book series is a study of such race-codes or race elements and is thus invaluable for illuminating race studies and the Victorian, social Darwinist ideology that tells us that blood will out.

²³ And not even Harry — who, if we read the book, starts out by assuming that Snape does not like him, only to draw even more dismal conclusions as the series proceeds.

²⁴ See for a discussion, particularly of Milton and also concerning asphodel and snakes, as well as with reference to ancient authors and aphrodisiac effects, the eponymous essay in Graves. See more recently Phillips, who refers to Homer's *Odyssey*, Book 24, with the tiniest of worries on the part of this reader, given Phillips' assumption that some parts of Homer's poem were, for example, by the poet's hand, as he implies, and some not, begging the Homer question entirely. All is redeemed, however, by the sections "Daffodils and Ashes." And see also Dweck, who refers to the invocation of "the daffodil as a potent of death" in Herrick's *Hesperides*, "probably connecting the flower with the asphodel, which the ancient Greeks planted near tombs" (24). And the connection then with asphodel explicates the inclusion of the daffodil in the list of "every flower that sad imbroidrie wears" in Milton's "Lycidas," reading "Bid *Amaranthus* all his beauties shed, / And daffadillies fill their cups with tears, / To strew the laureate herse where *Lycid* lies" (ll. 148-151).

²⁵ William Carlos Williams, "Asphodel, That Greeny Flower" (1955), begins as follows: "Of asphodel, that greeny flower, / like a buttercup / upon its branching stem — / save that it's green and wooden — / I come, my sweet, / to sing to you. / We lived long together / a life filled, / if you will, / with flowers. So that / I was cheered / when I came first to know / that there were flowers also / in hell..." (ll. 1-14).

²⁶ „Du, Geist der Erde, bist mir näher; / ... / Schon glüh ich wie von neuem Wein“ (*Faust* 158).

²⁷ „Ich fühle ganz mein Herz dir hingegeben! / Du mußt! Du mußt! Und kostet' es mein Leben!“ (*Faust* 158).

²⁸ „Du flehst er atmend, mich zu schauen, / Meine Stimme zu hören, mein Antlitz zu sehn; / Mich neigt dein mächtig Seelenflehn: / Da bin ich! — Welch erbärmlich Grauen / Faßt Übermenschen dich! Wo ist der Seele Ruf? / Wo ist die Brust, die eine Welt in sich erschuf / Und trug und hefte? Die mit Freudebeben / Erschwoll, sich uns, den Geistern, gleichzuheben? / Wo bist du, Faust, des Stimme mit erklang, / Der sich an mich mit allen Kräften drang? / Bist du es, der, von meinem Hauch unwittert, / In allen Lebenstreifen zittert, / Ein furchtsam weggekrümmter Wurm?“ (*Faust* 159).

²⁹ See Heidegger's own reflection on Goethe (and Herder) in *Being and Time* for this reference.

³⁰ See Babich, « Vers une éthique ». An English version is forthcoming as “Solicitude: Heideggerian Care and Assistance” in Paul Fairfield and Saulius Geniusas, eds., *Relational Hermeneutics: Essays in Comparative Philosophy* (London: Bloomsbury, 2018).

³¹ See Babich, “Who is Nietzsche's Archilochus? Lyric Poetry, Quantitational Rhythm, and the Problem of the Subject in *The Birth of Tragedy*,” which is forthcoming in Charles Bambach and Theodore George, eds., *Philosophy and Poetry* (Albany: State University of New York Press, 2018). And see as well, for the German, Babich, „Nietzsches Lyrik. Archilochus, Musik, Metrik.“

³² Of course I have argued that this was otherwise for Nietzsche, and I read Carl Dahlhaus as in part supporting a similar claim. I have made this argument for some time, but see in addition the last three chapters of my *The Hallelujah Effect* and „Wort und Musik.“

³³ This assumption that ancient music must be presented in a script holds even with respect to more recent work on ancient Greek music; it can be seen in the coffee-table sized sourcebook collection curated by Pöhlman and West.

³⁴ Nietzsche, “Greek Music Drama.” See Friedrich Nietzsche, “On Music and Word” [„Über Musik und Wort“], in Dahlhaus, 106-119, esp. 107. This modern presumption leads us astray when it comes to the ancients. As Nietzsche writes in “On Music and Word,” to speak of anything like a “necessary relation between poem and music ... makes no sense for the two worlds of tone and image are too remote from each other to enter more than an external relationship. The poem is only a symbol and related to the music like the Egyptian hieroglyph of courage to a courageous soldier” (Dahlhaus 112).

³⁵ This is an older question, going back to Rousseau and earlier still. See, for a related discussion with respect to Nietzsche, Corbier.

³⁶ Of course this goes back to Herder, to Rousseau, and to others. Nor is this claim dissimilar to points Claude Calame also makes, if Calame himself is not reading Nietzsche, and if his references are more mainstream or comparative, indeed concerned with gender in addition to his intriguing reflections on ethnophilology and ‘anthropoesis’, as he traces his own reading to Friedrich Max Müller. Calame also follows Nagy. See Calame, « Chanter », esp. 72, and see too Calame, « Le chant choral ». I also recommend, in particular, Miller, as well as several contributions to Budelmann, especially Battezzato.

³⁷ „1) Aus dem Volksleben tritt die orchestrisch-chorische Musik in den Agon ein.2) Es kommt die reine Instrumentalmusik hinzu.3) Das System der Tonarten erweitert sich durch phryg. Musik.4) Von hier an findet eine Notirung der Musik, Notensystem des Alphabets, statt ...“

³⁸ Koller names this a „Betönungsakzent.“ See Amy M. Dale’s several studies. There are other traditions as well, including the French, complete with elaborate articulations of positions and figures, especially in Maurice Emmanuel on dance, in addition to the Italian. This is not to say that Koller, any more than Dale, cites Nietzsche’s inspiration. Nor indeed, when it comes to ancient Greek lyric poetry, the late Martin West. But the connection remains, via Lloyd-Jones (206f.) and Maas among others, such as Bornmann.

³⁹ „Der Rhythm. Ictus ist nicht bezeugt, äußert keine Wirkungen, wird vielmehr geradezu ausgeschlossen.“

⁴⁰ Thus Koller differs in his return to the 19th century schema antecedent to Nietzsche, corresponding less to ancient Greek music and word than to the relation between music and poetic word in German (or French or English or Italian), precisely where the word *can be*, as Nietzsche claimed that for the ancient Greeks it could not be, *distinguished* from the music. Koller evinces several differences from both Nietzsche and Dale, as he himself centers on the figurative aspect of the various muses as such, fairly romantically. Despite Koller’s (more modernistic) insistence on the notion of a separate musical melody imposed upon the melody that is inherent to the words (Koller 12), he agrees with both Nietzsche and Dale, underlining that the same musical melodies, be they supervenient or not, would have been constrained to follow (and there is no departure from the dicta of antiquity) the melody of the words themselves. For Koller, and still more for today’s readers, one comes to grief with modern sensibilities on the variations between poetic meter. Thus Koller invokes a certain poetic sovereignty (we speak, in English, of poetic license), entailing the frustrations of parsing this musicality via metric or quantity. Koller cites Howald on Humbolt’s *Agamemnon* as support for this assertion (cf. Koller 13). If Koller is subsequently absorbed with a rather literalizing apotheosis of dancing maidens and nymphs as the muses ‘themselves’ (15 and 17ff, 25ff, etc.), which he invokes as the best way to understand the meaning of *mousiké techné*, these

metaphorically incarnate muses do not quite correspond to, even as they represent, the breadth of ancient Greek *mousiké*. See Babich, *Mousiké techné* as well as the last three chapters in *The Hallelujah Effect* and, most recently, „Nietzsches Lyrik. Archilocus, Musik, Metrik.“ For his part, Howald (whom Koller does quote) cites Georgiades who (as I show elsewhere) returns the argument to Nietzsche. The point here, as Howald makes it, is that we perhaps cannot have ears for this via „Akzent,“ i.e. what Nietzsche called ‚Iktus‘.

⁴¹ „Warum stellen wir die Musik nicht neben das Wort, sondern in das Wort?“

⁴² „Die Lyrik ist älteste Form der Poesie.“

⁴³ „4fach.“

⁴⁴ Illich writes that “Pre-literate Greek speechmaking and epic singing were based not on visual memory but on the recollection of formulas uttered to the rhythm of a lyre” (*Vineyard* 38). In his notes he refers to Peabody.

⁴⁵ Marcel Jousse, a Jesuit priest, was student of Marcel Mauss and an ethnographer in the spirit (today largely channeled by Bruno Latour) of the enterprise of turning the lens of anthropology (and sociology) on not only the other but also the observer: ourselves. See Jousse, *Oral Style*, and see too Meschonnic. With reference to Nietzsche, including a discussion of Jousse, see Kremer-Marietti.

⁴⁶ The reference is to Jousse, *L'Anthropologie du geste*.

⁴⁷ As Illich continues here, Jousse “first explored the connection between movement and memory (« Le Style oral rythmique et mnémotechnique chez les verbo-moteurs, » *Archives de Philosophie*, 2 [1924]: 1-240) and then the dissymmetric, bilateral nature of these movements corresponding to voice rhythms (« Le Bilatéralisme humain et l'anthropologie du langage, » *Revue anthropologique*, Aug.-Sept. 1940, p. 1-30). His influence on the young Milman Parry during the late 1920s led Parry to develop his theory on orality” (*Vineyard* 61, note 40).

⁴⁸ „Je mehr Sinn für natürliche Causalität stat magischer Causalität erwacht, um so mehr tritt der Rhythmus zurück.“ Thus Nietzsche traces a poetic declination from “Empedocles,” who, as Nietzsche recounts, “is almost wholly a poet to Plato who is yet half a poet, in interim as prose comes to be rhythmic, Democritus with a metrical resonance whereby Aristotle shows the abstraction from the rhythmic and the growth of pure reason.” („Empedokles, der noch fast ganz Dichter ist, Plato, der noch halb Dichter is u. bisweilen in Prosa rhythmische wird, Demokrit mit metrischem Anklang, Aristoteles zeigen das Abnehmen des Rhythmischen, Zunahme der reinen Vernunft“ („Griechische Lyriker,“ *Werke* 380).

⁴⁹ See for discussion and further references, Babich, “Adorno’s Radio Phenomenology.”

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